

Resin-catalysed Hydrolysis of Ethyl Formate in Dioxane-Water Medium

M. S. METWALLY^a, A. ABDEL RAZIK^{*b}, M. F. EL-HADI^a and M. A. EL-WARDANY^a

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Al-Azhar University, Cairo, Egypt

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Cairo University, Giza, Egypt

Manuscript received 25 June 1991, accepted 29 July 1993

Kinetics of the reaction between a newly synthesised sulphonated cation exchange resin and ethyl formate solution have been studied in dioxane-water mixtures of varying compositions of dioxane (0–45%, v/v) at different temperatures (20–40°). The order of the reaction in the heterogeneous catalysis by the resin was found to be the same as in the homogeneous catalysis by a dissolved electrolyte. The rate constant increased with the increase in resin concentration and decreased with increasing percentage of dioxane. Activation parameters were evaluated and trends of variation in these parameters and in hydrolysis rates have been discussed in terms of solvation effects and the dielectric behaviour of the medium.

The enhancement of the rate of hydrolysis of esters and amides associated with increasing ratio of aprotic component of binary solvent mixtures has been studied by a number of workers^{1,2}. According to the theory of Parker², the rate of such reactions in which the transition state passes through large polarization should be faster in aprotic than in protic solvents. However, contradictory views were presented by Hughes and Ingold³ and Laidler and Landskroener⁴ who suggested that the rate of such reactions should increase with increasing dielectric constant of the medium. Singh *et al.*⁵ observed that the rates of acid-catalysed hydrolysis of ethyl formate in aquo-organic solvent mixtures were enhanced only in the low concentration region of DMSO as aprotic constituent and decreased steadily beyond 8 mole percent of the organic co-solvent. With DMF as the aprotic constituent, however, the rate decreased steadily with increasing percentage of DMF in the binary mixture⁶. Thus depending on the type of co-solvent, the rates of acid-catalysed hydrolysis of ethyl formate may or may not be enhanced by increasing mole percent of the aprotic solvent.

In view of the various and even contradictory

views, it was thought proper to study the effect of some other aprotic solvent, such as dioxane on the hydrolysis of ethyl formate catalysed by cation exchange sulphonated resin in the H⁺ form and to investigate solvent effects on reaction mechanism and on the catalytic properties of the resin. The cation exchange resin used in the present study was prepared by sulphonation of acrylonitrile-butadiene-styrene copolymer previously cross-linked with phenol-formaldehyde resin. Method of preparation of the resin and its application in the catalysed hydrolysis of ethyl acetate in aqueous solution has been published by the authors elsewhere⁷.

Results and Discussion

The heterogeneous catalysed hydrolysis of ethyl formate was found to obey a first order reaction. To determine the order of the reaction with respect to the solid catalyst, solutions containing varying weights of exchange resin were stirred continuously at a constant rate. The results (Table 1) indicate first order reaction with respect to resin concentration.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF WT. RESIN/VOL SOLUTION ON THE HYDROLYSIS OF 0.2 M ETHYL FORMATE IN 30% DIOXANE AT 30°

Wt. Resin g	Rate constant $K_r \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	Catalyst efficiency q
1	3.22	1.29
2	3.37	1.23
3	3.78	1.15
4	4.15	0.94
5	4.38	0.82

The efficiency of the resin (q) which is the ratio of the reaction rate constants in the heterogeneous and the homogeneous systems with equivalent amounts of catalyst, is larger than unity for resin concentrations up to 3 g, indicating that in this resin concentration range, the ion exchanger as a catalyst is more effective than an equivalent amount of hydrochloric acid in the process of ester hydrolysis. Excess amount of resin, however, seems to prevent the hydrolysis of the ester, thus decreasing the efficiency of the catalyst.

Rate constant for the resin catalysed hydrolysis of ethyl formate in various water-dioxane mixtures at temperatures 20, 30 and 40° are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2—SPECIFIC RATE CONSTANT (k) VALUES FOR THE RESIN CATALYSED HYDROLYSIS OF ETHYL FORMATE IN WATER-DIOXANE MIXTURES

Dioxane %(v/v)	$k \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$		
	20°	30°	40°
0	4.61	7.79	14.83
15	3.33	4.11	7.41
30	2.59	3.37	5.70
45	1.90	2.30	3.82

It is seen from Table 2 that for the temperatures studied, the reaction rate is inhibited by increasing the concentration of the organic co-solvent. This behaviour, generally associated with electrostatically influenced rates, is mainly due to selective solvation by the higher dielectric (water) mixed solvent⁸. The decrease of rate constant with increasing concentration of dioxane in the mixture can be explained by the marked

decrease in the bulk dielectric constant of the medium associated with increasing percentage of dioxane on account of its low value compared to water. This decrease of dielectric may lower the concentration of highly polar transition state and thereby the rate is decreased (Table 3). Graphical representation of the variation of rate

Fig. 1. Variation of $\log k$ with mole percent of dioxane in the mixture.

constant ($\log k$) with mole percent of dioxane in the mixture is shown in Fig. 1. The lower rate of decrease above 8 mole percent (30% dioxane by volume) may be attributed to greater extent of solvation changes in the transition state compared to the initial state, a factor which becomes significant only after the addition of a considerable amount of dioxane (above 8 mole percent).

TABLE 3—SPECIFIC RATE CONSTANT (k), VALUES FOR THE RESIN CATALYSED HYDROLYSIS OF ETHYL FORMATE IN WATER-DIOXANE MIXTURES AND THE CORRESPONDING DIELECTRIC CONSTANTS*

Dioxane mol %	30°		40°	
	$3 + \log k$	D	$3 + \log k$	D
0	0.892	76.75	1.171	73.28
3.58	0.614	63.75	0.870	60.50
8.04	0.528	51.5	0.756	49.00
13.33	0.362	39.5	0.583	37.50

*Ref. 10.

Solvation effect and activation parameters :

The Arrhenius activation energy (E_a) also called isocomposition activation energy, was calculated from the slope of the straight line obtained by plotting $\log k$ against $1/T$. The entropy (ΔS^*) and enthalpy (ΔH^*) of activation were calculated using the equation⁹,

$$k_r = \frac{KT}{k} e^{\Delta S^*/R} e^{-\Delta H^*/RT}$$

The values of ΔG^* , the free energy of activation, were then obtained by $\Delta G^* = \Delta H^* - T\Delta S^*$.

The results are presented in Table 4. Plot of E_a values against mole percent of dioxane indicates a uniform decrease in the E_a values after a molar composition of 8 mole % dioxane (Fig. 2). This may be attributed to the very slow solvation process in the mixture upto 8 mole % dioxane and since the activated complex is a large cation, it is more vulnerable to be solvated compared to the reactants by the aprotic solvents. This view regarding greater solvation of transition state by increasing percent of dioxane is further supported from entropy of activation changes. It is noticed that the entropy of activation decreases with increasing concentration of dioxane which is in conformity with the above view.

TABLE 4—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR ETHYL FORMATE IN WATER-DIOXANE MIXTURES

Dioxane %(v/v)	E_a kJ mol	ΔH^* kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔG^* kJ mol ⁻¹ at 30°	$-\Delta S^*$ J mol K ⁻¹ at 30°
0	39.68	37.16	59.10	72.40
15	27.54	25.02	60.75	117.92
30	25.49	22.97	60.99	125.48
45	23.73	21.21	62.18	135.21

Although the effect of variation of solvent composition on ΔG^* is negligible, the effect on ΔS^* and ΔH^* cannot be ignored. The non-linear dependence of these activation parameters on the mole percent of the organic cosolvent (Fig. 2) indicates specific solvation¹¹ occurring in the

Fig. 2. Variation of activation parameters with mole percent of dioxane in the mixture.

medium. Similar variation in activation parameters was reported by Singh *et al.*⁶ in their study of the homogeneous acid catalysis of ethyl formate in DMF-water medium and by other authors for different hydrolysis reactions in aquo-organic solvents¹².

The large negative values of entropy of activation indicate loss in internal entropy of the ester molecule accompanying its fixation on the skeleton of the resin catalyst in the formation of the transition state, viz. the activated complex within the resin.

In general, one may conclude that the rate of resin catalysed hydrolysis of ethyl formate and variation of activation parameters can be explained on the basis of solvent-solute interaction, solvation of the transition state and the dielectric behaviour of the medium.

Experimental

The sulphonated cation exchange resin in the hydrogen form was used as a catalyst. The average mesh size of the resin was 250–420 μm and its exchange capacity was 3.48 meq g^{-1} .

The specific rate constants were determined in different resin solvent mixtures containing 0–45 % (v/v) dioxane at temperatures 20, 30 and 40° ($\pm 0.1^\circ$). The rate of reaction was followed by observing the change in resistance of the reaction mixture using a conductivity bridge. Rate constants were calculated using the equation^{9,13},

$$K_f = \frac{2.303}{t} \log \frac{R_t(R_\infty - R_0)}{R_0(R_\infty - R_t)}$$

where R_t is the resistance at time t , R_0 the resistance at zero time and R_∞ the resistance at infinite time noted at equilibrium (i.e. when no change in resistance was observed after sufficient

lapse of time). Total order of the reaction was determined by using the fractional-life method⁹.

References

1. J. E. QINLAN and E. S. AMIS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 4182; R. K. WOLFORD, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1964, **68**, 3392; D. D. ROBERTS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1964, **29**, 2039; S. C. RAKSHIT and M. K. SARKAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 605; L. SINGH, R. T. SINGH, R. K. SINGH and R. C. JHA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 372; D. D. ROBERTS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, **31**, 4037.
2. A. J. PARKER, *Quart. Rev.*, 1962, **16**, 163.
3. C. K. INGOLD, "Structure and Mechanism in Organic Chemistry", Bell, London, 1953.
4. K. J. LAIDLER and P. A. LANDSKROENER, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1956, **52**, 200.
5. L. SINGH, R. T. SINGH and R. C. JHA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 1089.
6. L. SINGH, R. T. SINGH and R. C. JHA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **57**, 966.
7. M. S. METWALLY, M. F. EL-HADI, M. A. EL-WARDANY and A. A. RAZIK, *J. Materials Sci.*, 1990, **25**, 4223.
8. M. M. ELSEMONGY, M. S. A. ELAMAYEM and M. MOUSSA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 1130.
9. A. A. FROST and R. G. PEARSON, "Kinetics and Mechanism", Wiley, New York, pp. 37, 41, 99, 101.
10. G. AKERLOF and O. A. SHORT, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **58**, 1241; Y. M. GIRIS, Ph.D. Thesis, Cairo University, 1968.
11. R. K. HUDSON and B. J. SAVILLE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 4114.
12. E. TOMMILA, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1955, **9**, 975; J. B. HYNE and R. E. ROBERTSON, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1956, **34**, 863; M. M. ELSEMONGY, M. S. A. ELAMAYEM and M. N. H. MOUSA, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1975, **95**, 215.
13. V. SENTIYA and R. P. SHUKLA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 1130.